

FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF THE DISEASE IN PATIENCE WITH CHRONIC HEART FAILURE RESISTANT TO ADP-INDUCED PLATELET AGGREGATION

Alyavi A.L.
Khojanova Sh.I.
Reymbaeva. A.A.
Jabbarov A.A.
Makhsudova M.X.
Saydaliev R.S.
Qodirova SH.A.
Tursunova L.D

Tashkent medical Academy, Tashkent
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Introduction. The close relationship between the processes of atherogenesis and thrombosis makes it pathogenetically justified to conduct long-term antithrombotic therapy for the purpose of secondary prevention of cardiovascular complications (CVD). The leading role in this belongs to drugs that inhibit platelet aggregation. Determination of ADP-induced platelet aggregation allows to evaluate the degree of platelet activation and adequacy of antiplatelet therapy.

Purpose of work. To study ADP-induced platelet aggregation in patients with chronic heart failure .

Material and methods of research. The study included 60 patients with chronic heart failure (30 women and 30 men, mean age was 59.3 ± 4.2 years) who were in the therapeutic Department of the Republican clinical hospital №1(1 - RKB). All patients received aspirin at a dose of 75-100 mg / day. The criterion for evaluating the effectiveness of antiplatelet therapy was a decrease in the aggregatogram (percentage of aggregation) from the initial 3-4 times. The degree of platelet aggregation induced by ADP was determined by a two-channel laser analyzer of platelet aggregation LA230 "Biola". Normal activity limits the aggregation process of platelets with the addition of ADP amount to 55-65%. Statistical processing of the results of the study was carried out using the statistical software package Statistica 6.0.

Research result. ADP-induced platelet aggregation before the start of aspirin therapy in the examined patients was $73.5 \pm 2.5\%$. Moreover, 51 (85%) of 60 patients had ADP-induced platelet aggregation significantly higher than normal – $78.0 \pm 2.1\%$. After 10 days of aspirin therapy, ADP-induced platelet aggregation was found to be $35.4 \pm 1.7\%$. In 9 (16%) patients the proportion of ADF-induced aggregation remained high – $74.3 \pm 1.6\%$. These 9 patients were

assigned to have clopidogrel 75 mg/day. After 7 days of therapy with clopidogrel, the study of ADP-induced platelet aggregation showed that the proportion of platelet aggregation significantly decreased ($p < 0.001$) and amounted to $27.5 \pm 1.6\%$. After a year of aspirin therapy, it was found that ADP-induced aggregation was $36.3 \pm 1.2\%$. In 4 (7%) patients the proportion of ADP-induced aggregation remained high – $54.2 \pm 1.5\%$. These 4 patients were also assigned clopidogrel 75 mg / day.

Conclusion. Given the high rates of ADP-induced aggregation of platelets induced aggregation of thrombocytes in $\frac{1}{4}$ of patients with chronic heart failure, it is necessary to monitor antithrombotic therapy in these patients to study this indicator aggregatogram to determine the adequacy of the medical treatment.

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